

Deliverable**EuroMix****Grant Agreement n°633172**

Collaborative project H2020-SFS-2014-2

Deliverable 1.1 – Gender Plan**Gender Plan**

WP 1– Management

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	V
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

Deliverable D1.1

Gender Plan

February 2016

Deliverable 10.1

Gender plan

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Summary

H2020 seeks to support gender equality by encouraging equal participation of men and women in research teams at all levels.

The EuroMix project will support gender equality through the implementation of its Gender Plan.

Gender Plan

- Appoint a gender counsellor: Eglė Baecke-Eimontaitė from FreshFel Europe.
The gender counsellor:
 - Keeps up-to-date with latest EU legislation and strategic plans on gender equality;
 - Provides confidential advice to project participants, both male and female, on work issues related to gender equality, such as work-life balance, geographical mobility, different career structures, etc.;
 - Seeks advice from the commission in case of a gender related dispute;
 - Monitors statistics of gender representation amongst project partners to be reported to project coordinator for each periodic review;
 - The gender councillor reports to the coordinator (Jacob van Klaveren)
- Each partner organisation will be responsible for ensuring that their conduct is in accordance with their national legislation and with EU legislation on gender equality
- Each partner organisation will ensure that during recruitment to roles relating to the project, both sexes have equal opportunity to apply for the role
- The project team will attempt, where possible, to arrange project meetings and activities in a manner that supports the participation of all project participants e.g. use of tele/video-conferencing facilities, scheduling meetings to avoid national or school holidays
- Gender equality will be a regular item on the agenda of the Project Management Committee meetings
- In the EuroMix project 4 out of 10 WP leaders are females. The EuroMix WP-leaders do have to appoint a deputy WP-leader. The WP-leaders will aim at 50% of the deputy WP leaders to be females.